

were filtered off and purified by repeated washings with hot ethanol. Acetone, benzene, and glacial acetic acid were found unsuitable for crystallisation.

Products were not obtained in 60 days time, using *p*-nitroaniline and 8-hydroxyquinaldine with resorcyaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, and 1-hydroxy-2-naphthaldehyde; 8-hydroxyquinaldine and *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde; reaction with anthranilic acid and *o*-anisidine also failed to afford any product. Desired products also could not be obtained when 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was allowed to react with *p*-nitroaniline and 8-hydroxyquinoline. Failure of the reaction could in most of the cases be attributed to insufficient solubility of the Schiff's base in 95% ethanol.

The compounds can be represented by the general structural formula A (*vide supra*).

TABLE I

Substituted 7- α -anilino-8-quinaldinols and quinolinols.

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Formula.	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen.	
							Found.	Calc.
1.	Me	Ph	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	203°	12.3%	9.6	10.91
2.	..	..	<i>o</i> -OMe	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃	140°	38.0	6.8	7.57
3.	..	..	-C ₅ H ₂ NS or	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	175°	14.0	12.6	12.10
4.	..	..	-C ₅ H ₄ N or	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃	160°d	34.0	11.8	12.30
5.	..	<i>m</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	203°	7.0	9.90	10.50
6.	..	..	-C ₅ H ₂ NS or	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	196°	28.0	10.91	11.57
7.	..	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	-C ₅ H ₂ NS or	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	185°	22.0	11.02	11.57
8.	..	-C ₄ H ₃ O or	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂	170°	35.0	10.70	11.20
9.	H	-C ₄ H ₃ O or	-C ₅ H ₂ NS or	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	175°	43.0	12.25	12.70
10.	..	-C ₄ H ₃ O or	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂	208°	32.0	10.81	11.62
11.	..	-C ₇ H ₇ O ₂ or	-C ₅ H ₂ NS or	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	186°	25.0	10.3	11.08

Spot tests.—Colour reactions with H₂SO₄ (conc.), HNO₃ (conc.), and 1% ferric chloride being specific, spot tests were carried out for each of the products. In the particular series all the three spot tests were found to be quite conclusive regarding the presence of the desired products.

TABLE II

No.	Time for first sign of ppt.	Colour reaction with		
		H ₂ SO ₄ .	HNO ₃ .	1% FeCl ₃ .
1.	6 days	Red	Yellow	Light green in alc. only
2.	33	Light red	Deep violet	Green
3.	17	Red	Yellow	"
4.	66	"	"	"
5.	35	Light red	"	"
6.	25	"	"	"
7.	19	Red	"	"
8.	2	Violet	Deep yellow	"
9.	2	"	Yellow	"
10.	2	Red	Violet	Green in alc. only
11.	10.5	"	Yellow	Green

The study yielded the following conclusions :

The most active amine was found to be *p*-nitroaniline in all cases studied by variations of the aldehyde portions (using substituted benzaldehydes or furfural in place of benzaldehyde) or by using 8-hydroxyquinaldine in place of 8-quinolinol.

Parallel reactions, when carried out by using 8-hydroxyquinaldine, were generally found to be much slower. This means that apart from the well-known effect of the steric hindrance, exerted by a substituent in the 2-position in 8-quinolinol, the methyl group has the effect of decreasing the reactivity of the molecule at position-7.

Methoxy substituents in the aldehyde part do not seriously affect the rate of the reaction (cf. vanillin and benzaldehyde with 2-aminothiazole when acted upon 8-quinolinol).

Furfural approaches the reactivity of benzaldehyde in the Betti reaction and even exceeds it in two cases (cf. furfural and benzaldehyde with *m*-nitroaniline and *p*-nitroaniline, the time of reaction is shorter in both the cases with furfural).